

MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR OF TRANSMISSION UNITS AND MECHANISMS

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Abstract: The main faults of transmission units., Clutch failure, Faults in the gearbox and distribution box, Diagnostics of transmission units, Maintenance of transmission units, Maintenance of gearbox and distribution box.

Key words: clutch failure and maintenance, transmission failure and maintenance, cardan transmission failure and maintenance, main drive failure and maintenance, front drive axle failure and maintenance.

As we know, the main units of the car transmission include clutch, cardan transmission, pinion or hydromechanical gearbox, transfer case and drive axle. Automotive transmission units (Figures 1 and 2) account for 10...15% of all failures and 40% of total maintenance labor and material costs [1].

Figure 1. Rear wheel drive car transmission:

I-engine, II-clutch, III-transmission, IV-cardan transmission, V-Differential and rear axle together with the main transmission. 1-elastic coupling, 2-slot joint, 3-

front cardan shaft, 4-suspension bearing, 5-front cardan joint, 6-rear cardan shaft,
7-rear cardan joint, 8-half axles,
9-rear drive wheels

Figure 2. Front wheel drive car transmission:

I-engine, II-clutch, III-gear box, IV-main gear and differential, V-shafts with equal angular velocity left and right, VI-front driving wheels

The main faults of transmission units. Malfunctions in the transmission units occur during the operation of the car, as well as due to damage, corrosion or breakage of some parts. Malfunctions are eliminated as a result of performing adjustments that restore the initial state of units or replacing some details.

Clutch failure. Malfunctions often occur as a result of its incomplete connection or incomplete disconnection. In the absence of a full clutch, the torque is not fully transmitted from the engine, when the clutch is released, the car starts very slowly or cannot start at all, and the drive disc in the clutch wears out very quickly and fails in a short period of time [2].

Due to the complete non-separability of the coupling, when connecting the gears, metal is joined with percussion and difficulty, and it is required to act on the lever with more force. These failures are caused by misalignment of the clutch separation mechanism, oil contact or corrosion of the drive disk. In cars with a hydraulic clutch, as a result of corrosion of the inner surface of the head and working

cylinders, pistons and cuffs, air may enter the clutch or partial leakage of fluid from the system may cause the clutch to malfunction.

Faults in the gearbox and distribution box. These malfunctions cause difficulties in switching transmissions, transmissions break off by themselves or cause noise during operation. Due to the loosening of the bolts in the fork or head of the interchangeable coupling mechanism, the jamming of the fasteners, the wear of gears, bearings and bushings, the transmission wears out. Corrosion on the side of the teeth of the synchronizer clutch and sprockets and on the working surfaces causes the gears to break off due to the incomplete connection of the gears, the loosening of the locking springs. The noise in the gearbox is caused by corrosion and breakage of the working surfaces of the shaft bearings and gear teeth, as well as a decrease in the oil level [2-3].

Malfunctions of main and cardan transmissions, differentials, half-axes and joints with equal angular velocity. Malfunctions occur as a result of long-term use without timely technical maintenance or poor-quality TCK. Examples of malfunctions in the main transmission and differential are the erosion or breakage of gear teeth, differential cross-piece and bearings, as well as a violation of the tightness of the main transmission pulleys. All of them are manifested by increased noise in the rear axle housing during movement. The presence of knocks and knocks when the car starts, turns or moves indicates malfunctions in cardan transmissions or hinges with equal angular speed. These malfunctions are caused by a lot of wear of cross shafts and hinge cups, if the balance of the cardan shaft is disturbed, strong vibrations and noises are formed in the transmission. The main faults in half-axes are the wear of their splines [4].

Diagnostics of transmission units. Diagnostics makes it possible to determine the technical condition of units and draw a conclusion about their reusability after performing the necessary adjustments. Transmission units can be checked while the car is moving, as well as on a special device. Depending on the design of the

diagnostic equipment, it is possible to determine the degree of wear of the clutch, gearbox, cardan transmission and rear axle. Diagnostic work is mainly carried out from the bottom of the car (Fig. 3) [1].

Figure 3. External diagnostics of the car transmission

A simple way to diagnose the transmission is to measure the circular clearances in the drive axle, cardan shaft, and gearbox using the tool shown in Figure 4. The tool consists of a dynamometric device with a comprehensive scope and movable and fixed jaws that make it up. The measuring scope is put on the semi-axle or cardan shaft under inspection, and then it is fixed to the assembly detail by pushing the movable jaw with the help of a worm [5-6].

To determine the backlash, the handle is turned with force, and when the spring sound detector sounds, the backlash is recorded by the gauge needle. The scale of the meter can be turned to an arbitrary angle. That is why, before measuring, it is necessary to zero the arrow of the instrument installed on the tested unit [6].

Figure 4. The tool for determining the circular backlash in the transmission:

1- movable and immovable jaws; 2-jaw fixing worm; 3-degree disc; 4-ring; 5-indicator; 6-dynamometric handle

Maintenance of transmission units. Servicing of transmission aggregates is carried out in the course of regular maintenance and technical service.

During the daily service, the transmission units are checked by starting the vehicle and switching gears while driving. the condition and tightness of the leading bridge is controlled.

In the 1st technical service, in addition to the daily maintenance work, the free travel path of the clutch shaft is checked and, if necessary, adjusted, and the running parts are lubricated with plastic materials. Transmission box, cardan transmission, distribution box, fastening of the rear axle casing, the condition of the seals are checked, the oil levels in the aggregates are adjusted [7-8].

In the 2nd, 3rd, 4th technical service, daily maintenance of transmission units and all work in the 1st technical service is performed, oil in the units is changed in accordance with the lubrication map. If faults are found in the aggregates, they are repaired to bring them to working condition.

In addition, we will consider the work performed on each transmission unit separately.

Maintenance of clutch coupling. During operation, the coupling is adjusted, but before that, the free path of the coupling shaft is checked. A ruler with two sliders is used for this. One end of the rod is attached to the floor of the cabin, and the pusher is attached to the landing pad [9]. The clutch lever is pressed until the resistance to

movement increases sharply, and this situation is recorded with the help of the second pusher. The distance between the two sliders of the ruler determines the free path of the wheel.

In modern GM-Uz cars, a hydraulic clutch is often used (Fig. 5).

Such a clutch is brought to the norm of full movement and free movement of the drive shaft. To determine the path of full movement, the distance-A is determined with the shaft of the coupling clutch to the lower part of the steering wheel, then the distance-V is determined by fully pressing the shaft. The difference between distances A and V should be 130-136 mm. If this distance differs from the norm, then the adjustment work is performed. The full travel path of the 3rd step is adjusted by loosening the 4th limit nut and turning the 5th support bolt [1-5].

Figure 5. Determining and adjusting the full and free travel path of the clutch shaft of a Nexia car

The path of free movement of the kick is adjusted by loosening the 2nd limiting nut and changing the length of the 1st rod. The free movement of the kick should be in the range of 8-15 mm.

In most passenger cars, the free travel of the clutch shaft is adjusted by changing the length of the working cylinder rod.

As a result of corrosion of pistons, pistons or cylinders, cracks occur in excess of the norm. Through them, air enters the guide of the clutch, and it is expelled through the air exhaust pipe of the working cylinder (Fig. 6) [8].

Figure 6. Bleeding the clutch guide:

1 working cylinder, 2 exhaust pipe

For this, the working cylinder is cleaned of dust and dirt. The fluid level is checked by opening the lid of the fluid reservoir in the clutch guide. It is 15-20 mm from the carved part. should not be below or below the "min" mark. The rubber cover of the exhaust valve of the working cylinder is removed, a rubber hose is inserted in its place, and one end is lowered into a glass container filled with brake fluid in the volume of 1/3...1/2. The travel rod is pressed and moved frequently until resistance is felt, that is, until the travel path of the rod does not change, then, while pressing the rod, the valve is turned 1/2...3/4 circles, and when the rod is pressed to

the end, the valve is fixed and the reaction is slowly released. This situation is continued until there are no more air bubbles in the glass container. During the operation, the brake fluid level in the tank is periodically checked and adjusted. Finally, the valve is hardened and removed from the hose [11].

Maintenance of gearbox and distribution box. How the boxes work is checked during the daily inspection and when the car is moving. Particular attention is paid to compactness of compactors, easy and noiseless connection of transmissions. There should be no extraneous knocks and noises during the operation of the tested aggregates. It is necessary to fully connect the gears of the extensions, it is not allowed to separate by itself.

The heat of the transmission case should be such that it does not burn the hand when the car is stopped.

In addition to daily maintenance and 1st technical service, in addition to monitoring, hearing, and checking the temperature, the box body is cleaned of dirt, the fastening points are checked and tightened, and the oil level is brought to the norm. 2, 3, 4-In addition to the above-mentioned works in the technical service, the oils in the boxes are replaced according to the map. This work is carried out at special workstations with hoists or viewing channels. The oil in the box is drained as soon as the engine stops, before the box has time to cool [12].

The oil level in the units is checked using a dipstick or through an inspection hole. If the oil level has decreased, clean oil is added and the soap channels are cleaned. Oil change is performed as follows: after draining the old oil in the box, 1...2 amount of washing oil is poured instead. One wheel of the rear axle of the car is raised, the engine is started and the first gear is engaged. The transmission starts to work, in this case the interior of the box is washed and cleaned of waste. After a few minutes, the washing oil is drained and clean oil is poured. During the oil change, the drain plug magnet is also cleaned.

The necessary position of the control levers of the distribution box is provided by adjusting the length of the levers. For this purpose, the towing fingers are released from the splints and separated from the fork. When the fasteners are fully engaged, the stocks are set to the fully engaged position. The levers are placed in the position where the gears are connected, and by turning the fork, the desired length of the puller is set. After that, the puller is put in place, the finger is splinted and fixed with a counter nut [9-11].

Maintenance of main and cardan transmissions. Cardan and main gears are checked while the car is moving. In this case, extraneous noises and knocks should not be observed when the order of transmission of torque in the transmission changes from traction to braking or vice versa.

During the maintenance of cardan transmissions, the fastening of the flanges of the cardan joint is checked and tightened. During maintenance, bearings of cardan joints and splined joints of shafts are lubricated.

Cardan joints of passenger cars are lubricated with transmission oil, Litol-24, plastic lubricant or other materials according to the manufacturer's instructions. The oil is injected into the cranium using a special syringe. It is sent until the oil leaks from the side of the transfer valve or under the bearing shells. If the car is equipped with snow joints that are not intended for oil filling, lubrication is carried out only when it is disassembled [11-12].

The oil level in the drive bridge crankcase is checked in 2, 3, 4-Technical service and filled up to the edge of the oil filler hole. Complete oil change is carried out in accordance with the lubrication map and when the working season changes. the process of changing the oil in the drive bridge crankcase is also performed on the basis of the technology adopted for other units of the transmission.

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